

Flexible, Transparent, and Bifacial Perovskite Solar Cells and Modules Using Wide-band gap FAPbBr₃ Perovskite Absorber

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Abstract

Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) offer impressive performance and flexibility thanks to their simple, low-temperature deposition methods. Their bandgap tunability allows for a wide range of applications, transitioning from opaque to transparent devices. This study introduces the first flexible, bifacial PSCs using FAPbBr_3 perovskite. We investigated the impact of optimizing electron and hole transport layers on the cells' bifaciality, transparency, and stability. PSCs achieved a maximum power conversion efficiency (PCE) of 6.8% and 18.7% under 1-Sun and under indoor light conditions (1200 lx), respectively, showing up to 98% bifaciality factor and an average visible transmittance (AVT) of 55%. Additionally, P1-P2-P3 laser ablation scheme has been developed on flexible PET substrate for perovskite solar modules showing PCE of 4.8% PCE and high geometrical fill factor (97.8%). These findings highlight the potential of flexible, bifacial PSCs for diverse applications like building-integrated photovoltaics (BIPV), agrivoltaics, automotive technology, wearable sensors, and Internet of things (IoT).

Keywords: flexible perovskite solar cells, window-integrated photovoltaic, Transparent photovoltaic (TPV), hole transport layer (HTL), average visible transmittance (AVT), wide-bandgap perovskite

Introduction

With growing global energy demand, it is necessary to move from fossil fuels to renewable energy resources. Solar energy is a promising solution and photovoltaics (PV) technology has made significant progress in recent years. Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) have achieved impressive power conversion efficiencies (PCEs) of up to 26% in a short timeframe^{1,2}. The low temperature processability of PSCs has facilitated the development of Flexible PSCs (Flex-PSCs), adding significant advantages over conventional photovoltaics³⁻⁵. Due to their low-cost⁶⁻⁸, high power-to-weight-ratio^{9,10}, and mechanical robustness^{11,12}, flex-PSCs are beneficial for areas where conventional photovoltaics are impractical such as wearable technology, portable power sources^{13,14}, space applications^{15,16}, and internet of things (IoT)^{17,18}. In addition, flex-PSCs are compatible with scalable and cost-effective manufacturing methods, like roll-to-roll printing techniques^{19,20}.

Another notable characteristic of PSCs is their remarkable band-gap tunability, which can be achieved through composition engineering²¹⁻²³. The incorporation of bromide and chloride into the perovskite composition allows for the creation of highly transparent perovskites with band gaps as high as 2.39 eV²². Furthermore, PSCs exhibit excellent performance in the blue-light region, making them well suited as light harvesters for diffused sunlight on cloudy days and low-intensity indoor lighting during nights²⁴⁻²⁶. This, combined with flexibility provide an easy installation option to seamlessly integrate PVs into surfaces such as building facades, windows and walls, sensors, electric vehicles, wearable devices, and smart displays and act as replacements for conventional energy sources^{21,24,27-30}.

The usage of transparent top electrode materials such as dielectric-metal-dielectric (DMD)^{31,32}, Ag-nanowire³³, and graphene-based electrodes³⁴ contributed to the advancement in semi-transparent flex-PSCs. Unlike opaque photovoltaics, semi-transparent photovoltaics (ST-PVs) aim to maximize both average visible transmittance (AVT) and PCE simultaneously, considering the trade-off between AVT and PCE^{29,35,36}. As AVT increases, the PCE decreases, at 100% AVT, there is no power conversion efficiency in the visible region. Recently, a new metric called Light Utilization Efficiency (LUE), has emerged, which represents the

product of PCE and AVT²⁹. LUE quantifies the potential of emergent ST-PV technologies in converting incoming visible light into electricity while maintaining rather high AVT. A suitable ST-PV for applications such as smart windows, low-power displays, and automotive industry ST-PV technology should guarantee AVT greater than 50-80%²⁹. Among the strategies to increase the AVT is thickness tuning, patterning, and bandgap tuning^{24,37,38}. The optimal bandgap range to achieve AVT values of 50-80% with bandgap tuning strategy is 2.18 and 2.32 eV²⁴. Formamidinium lead bromide (FAPbBr₃) perovskite, which has a band gap of around 2.3 eV, falls well within the optimal band gap range for achieving high AVT, and has already demonstrated AVT values exceeding 50%^{39,40}. The PCE of opaque FAPbBr₃ solar cells typically reaches around 10%⁴¹⁻⁴³. However, when using semitransparent back contact, PCE decreased to approximately 8%^{39,40,44}. This reduction in efficiency is primarily attributed to the lack of back-reflection of the metallic back contact, which results in the reduced collection of backscattered light for harvesting. Furthermore, semitransparent solar cells often employ a thinner absorber layer to enhance the AVT of the cell. FAPbBr₃-based semitransparent PSCs exhibit minimal angular dependence of PCE, making them highly attractive for window-integrated applications⁴⁰. When deposited on flexible substrates, these cells also experience a decrease in PCE, with the highest reported PCE of 5.0% for flexible opaque cells⁴⁵ and no PSCs that are both flexible and semitransparent have been reported using this perovskite (FAPbBr₃) to the best of our knowledge.

In this study, we fabricated flexible and bifacial PSCs using FAPbBr₃ perovskite as absorber. The devices have architecture of PET/ITO/SnO₂/FAPbBr₃/HTL/ITO (**Figure 1a**). First, we examined the impact of potassium (K) treatment on the SnO₂ used as electron transport layer (ETL). Secondly, we studied the effect of hole transport layer (HTL) on the device bifaciality factor and long-term stability. Lastly, we fabricated flexible, bifacial perovskite solar modules for the first time with high geometrical fill factor of 97.8%. The fabricated flex-ST-PSCs demonstrated high bifaciality factor achieving similar PCEs from both sides.

Results and Discussion

For SnO₂-based PSCs, interfacial treatment with potassium ionic salts has become a very common method to improve device performance⁴⁶. The cations and/or anions of these salts play various roles in increasing the performance of PSCs. For example, they can passivate defects in SnO₂ or perovskite layer, as well as act as preferred nuclei for perovskite formation by forming ionic bonds with perovskite precursors⁴⁶. For the first time, we investigated the effectiveness of potassium treatment in wide bandgap bromide-based perovskite FAPbBr₃, using potassium chloride (KCl) salt. **Figure 1b** presents the statistical analysis of the J-V parameters of the flex-ST-PSC devices, while **Table 1** provides a summary of these parameters. The data is based on 20 cells fabricated for each group. The devices treated with KCl delivered a higher J_{SC} and fill factor, leading to an overall enhancement in performance.

We have conducted photoluminescence (PL), XRD, and SEM characterization on the perovskite film with and without KCl treatment. **Figure 1c** displays PL spectra of perovskite samples. Both spectra exhibit similar characteristics, with a Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) of 0.118 for each sample. The PL data reveal that the perovskite's bandgap remains constant at 2.28 eV after KCl treatment, and the optical properties remained unchanged. Additionally, the XRD patterns of these samples, presented in **Figure 1d**, demonstrate consistent peak positions and intensities suggesting that KCl does not modify fundamental crystal structure. **Figure 1e** shows scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of FAPbBr₃ perovskite deposited on PET/ITO/SnO₂ without treatment and with KCl treatment. The SEM images suggest that KCl

of the perovskite layer is observed to increase from 550 nm for the control to 850 nm with the application of KCl treatment.

To gain better understanding of charge transportation and recombination process, we performed transient photovoltage (TPV) and transient photocurrent (TPC) measurements for control and KCl treated cells (**Figure S1**). **Figure 2f** illustrates the exponential voltage decay of cells measured at a light intensity equivalent to 1-sun. TPV decay is carried under V_{oc} condition therefore it is related to recombination of accumulated charge carriers at the perovskite/charge transport films interface⁴⁷. The charge carrier lifetime can be determined from the TPV data by fitting a single exponential decay equation ($\tau = \tau_0 e^{-\beta V_{oc}}$) where τ and β represent carrier lifetime and the constant decay, respectively⁴⁸. The KCl treated cell showed longer decay resulting from less recombination at the perovskite/ETL surface. TPC measurement, on the other hand, represents charge carrier extraction at the transport layers since it is conducted under J_{sc} condition⁴⁷. In this case faster TPC decay of KCl treated cells showcases higher charge extraction ability (**Figure S1 and Table S3**). The relation between charge carrier density and charge carrier lifetime in different light intensities, which is measured by TPV and TPC data, is illustrated in **Figure 1g**. As expected, carrier lifetime is increased when charge carrier density is reduced⁴⁸. It is evident from the corresponding figure that these two parameters are increased for K-treated solar cells.

Figure 1. (a) The schematic of flex-PSC cell architecture. (b) Box plots depicting minimum, first quartile, median, third quartile, and maximum photovoltaic parameters of the corresponding devices based on 20 devices fabricated for control and potassium treated PSCs measured at AM1.5G illumination condition under forward and reverse scan directions. PL spectra (c) and XRD patterns (d) of Glass/SnO₂/FAPBr₃ (control) and Glass/SnO₂/KCl/FAPBr₃ (KCl). (e)

Scanning electron microscopy images of the FAPbBr₃ perovskite film deposited on top of PET/ITO/SnO₂ (control) and PET/ITO/SnO₂/KCl (KCl). (f) Normalized transient photovoltage decay LED light with power density of 100 mW.cm⁻² (g) Carrier lifetime versus carrier density of solar cells.

Table 1. Summary of PV parameters of potassium treatment experiment.

Type		V _{oc} (V)	J _{sc} (mA.cm ⁻²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)
Control	Best Cell	1.39	7.13	62.07	6.10
	Mean± std	1.34± 0.06	6.23± 0.91	55.05± 6.93	4.62± 0.97
KCl	Best Cell	1.40	7.35	65.70	6.8
	Mean± std	1.34± 0.04	6.94± 0.25	62.12± 4.19	5.77± 0.59

Bifacial solar cells can be illuminated from both sides. The choice of HTL choice is essential in PSCs, as the alignment of the band structures between the HTL and the perovskite layer plays a critical role in determining the V_{oc} and performance of PSCs^{49,50}. However, in the case of bifacial solar cells with n-i-p architecture, the choice of HTL becomes even more crucial, particularly when bifaciality is claimed as potential way to increase the power generation thanks to albedo reflections^{51,52}. In bifacial operation mode, the parasitic absorption HTL can compromise the light harvesting of the perovskite absorber when the ST-PSC is illuminated from the ITO back-contact. Furthermore, the sputtering process used to deposit ITO can potentially cause damage to the HTL, leading to a decrease in overall device performance⁵³. To gain a deeper understanding of FAPbBr₃-based flex ST-PSCs, a comparative analysis was performed on two different HTLs: PTAA and Poly-TPD (PTPD).

Since the solar cells are transparent and bifacial, we measured them once from normal side (front illuminated) and once from the back electrode (back illuminated). The JV curves of the champion devices are illustrated under AM1.5G in **Figure 2 a and d** and under indoor conditions (1200 lx) in **Figure 2 b and e**. The JV curves shown in **Figure 2** represent the reverse bias scan directions. The external quantum efficiency for both HTLs when illuminated from the front and back contacts are shown in **Figure 2 c and f**. The bifaciality factor, defined as the ratio of integrated J_{sc} obtained from the EQE measurement of cells when illuminated from the front and back, was determined to be 96% for PTAA and 98% for PTPD. PTPD outperforms PTAA with the bifaciality factor approaching unity (Integrated J_{sc} of 6.90 mA.cm⁻² from front versus 7.01 mA.cm⁻² from back). In addition, the optical behavior of the full stack cells including transmittance and absorption is shown in **Figure 2 g and h**. The AVT of devices was calculated to be 55.3% for PTAA and 53.6% for PTPD devices. To ensure the validity of the measured EQE and reported AVT of devices, the EQE versus 1 – (Transmittance + Reflectance) is plotted on the **Figure S9** and the corresponding optical loss analysis of the cells illuminated from both sides is calculated and plotted in the **Figure S10**.

PSCs offer a distinct advantage in their ability to efficiently harness light in indoor and low-light conditions^{18,54}. Given that the indoor light spectrum mainly consists of blue light, perovskite solar cells demonstrate improved power conversion efficiency (PCE) under these conditions²³. We measured cells under indoor conditions from both sides (See **Table S5**). The best indoor efficiency obtained by the PTAA-based device with 18.7% front-illuminated PCE and 17.83% back-illuminated PCE. The capability of being

bifacial and flexible indoor PSCs opens up various potential low-light applications including smart home sensors, architectural integration, indoor agrivoltaics, wearable devices, and internet of things (IoT).

Figure 2. Bifaciality of solar cells. JV curves under AM1.5G and indoor conditions, and EQE of bifacial Flex-PSCs illuminated from front and back for PTAA (a-c) and PTPD (d-f). Transmittance and Reflectance spectra of solar cells with PTAA (g) and PTPD (h) as HTL.

To gain deeper insights into the role played by the HTL, particularly in investigating non-radiative recombination at the absorber/HTL interface, we conducted a comprehensive analysis using absolutely calibrated photoluminescence imaging^{55,56}. Specifically, three distinct stacks were examined: PET/SnO₂/KCl/Perovskite, PET/SnO₂/KCl/Perovskite/PTPD, and PET/SnO₂/KCl/Perovskite/PTAA. In **Figure 3a-c**, we present maps of the quasi-Fermi level splitting (QFLS), derived by locally fitting hyperspectral images of photoluminescence spectra emitted under 1-sun equivalent illumination using a blue LED (405nm). An absorptivity model, corresponding to an ideal root squared absorptivity convolved with sub-bandgap tail states, was employed, as established in the formalism developed by Katahara and Hillhouse

⁵⁷ whose use was already reported in previous works ^{55,58}. The reference sample exhibited a QFLS of 1.83 eV, while the incorporation of a transport layer led to the emergence of non-radiative recombination, resulting in a decrease of this parameter to 1.81 eV and 1.78 eV for PTPD and PTAA, respectively. These values align with those recently reported for transparent high-bandgap perovskite solar cells⁴⁴. Notably, the samples exhibited a high level of homogeneity, with standard deviations on the order of 0.003 eV or less for the perovskite sample. The average photoluminescence spectra, depicted in **Figure 3d** reveals a gradual decrease in absolute intensity after the addition of the HTL. Additionally, a slight blue shift in the photoluminescence maximum position is observed, potentially induced by the presence of organic passivation cations derived from chloride salts added at the interface⁴⁴. **Figure 3e** presents a comparison of optical data acquired on stacks and electrical data acquired on full devices. Radiative quasi-Fermi level splitting ($\Delta\mu_{\text{rad}}$) and radiative open circuit voltage ($V_{\text{oc,rad}}$) are reported as theoretical limits for optical measurements and upper limits for open-circuit voltage measured by electrical means. Further details on their definitions are provided in the SI. Concerning the optical measurements, the difference between the radiative limit and the measured samples is 120 meV for the half cell, increasing to 140 meV and 160 meV for PTPD and PTAA, respectively, indicating an increase of non-radiative losses⁵⁹. Notably, the V_{oc} of PTAA devices is higher compared to their PTPD counterparts, a behaviour that might be attributed to potentially more aggressive ITO sputtering in the case of PTPD. Further research on the effect of ITO sputtering damage on these HTLs is strongly recommended.

Figure 3. Photoluminescence Imaging Analysis. Hyperspectral measurements on the stacks ITO/SnO₂/KCl/FAPbBr₃ (pero), ITO/SnO₂/KCl/ FAPbBr₃/PTPD (PTPD) and ITO/SnO₂/KCl/ FAPbBr₃/PTAA (PTAA). quasi-Fermi level splitting ($\Delta\mu$) maps for (a) pero, (b) PTPD and (c) PTAA samples. (d) Photoluminescence average spectra for the three maps (e) quasi-Fermi level splitting (QFLS) values extracted from PL spectra compared with radiative QFLS $\Delta\mu_{\text{rad}}$, open circuit voltage V_{oc} and radiative open circuit voltage $V_{\text{oc,rad}}$.

The stability of the unencapsulated solar cells, stored under ISOS-D-1 conditions (room temperature, ambient conditions), was evaluated, and shown in **Figure 4a**. It was observed that all devices exhibited a slight increase in performance during the first week after fabrication, followed by a stabilization of efficiency over a period of 1000 hours. This could be attributed to recovering from sputtering damage⁶⁰ or the oxidation of the hole transport material⁶¹. To understand the adhesion between the HTL and ITO top electrode, we performed a cyclic bending test. The cyclic bending test is a standard procedure to determine the mechanical behavior of flex-PSCs¹². It has been reported that the PET/ITO substrates can sustain the cyclic bending test with a cylinder radius of above 14 mm without the reduction of conductivity, but performing the test with smaller radius of curvature results in the failure of ITO and substantial reduction of conductivity⁶². Thus, the bending test was performed with a curvature radius of 18 mm. Both PTAA and PTPD demonstrated stable performance in terms of adhesion to ITO, with both HTLs maintaining over 80% PCE even after 1200 bending cycles. PTPD surpassed the performance of the other HTLs by retaining 94% of its PCE after 1200 bending cycles.

Figure 4. (a) The stability measurement of solar cells with different HTLs under ISOS-1D conditions. (b) The normalized PCE of devices going through the mechanical bending test.

The mini modules we fabricated consist of two cells with a total active area of 2.9 cm² with the PET/ITO/SnO₂/KCl/FAPbBr₃/PTAA/ITO device architecture. The optimization of the laser parameters, including interconnection width and laser fluences have been carried out starting from a previous optimization procedure⁶³: a matrix of laser power as a function of pulse densities have been implemented for each etching process, moving around the starting values optimized in our previous works combining semitransparent and flexible substrates^{39,64}. We minimized the losses on the P2 process by applying 3 couple of lines by differing by 200 pulse density each, keeping the power density constant for all cases: especially for flexible substrate, the presence of valleys and hills at microscopic level is unavoidable at the

time of marking the lines, causing defocusing; therefore, the use of slightly different parameters help to homogenize the ablation, fundamental to reduce losses at the interconnections⁶⁵. By reducing scribe width and optimizing laser parameters, we attained 155 μm interconnection width (**Figure S7**), resulting in a geometrical fill factor of 97.83%. This laser precision enhances efficiency and paves the way for scalable, high-performance solar semi-transparent flexible modules. The champion module achieved a PCE of 4.8%, with a voltage of 2.7 V, a current density of 4.90 mA/cm^2 , and a fill factor (FF) of 72.75%. As far as our knowledge goes, this is the first flexible FAPbBr₃-based module reported. The current-voltage (IV) characteristics of the device and the photographic image of the module are presented in **Figure 5a and b**.

We plotted the PCE and AVT of various flexible ST-PSCs reported in the literature (**Table S2, Figure 5c**). Compared with the literature results, our device outperforms the existing flexible ST-SCs by 55% AVT and setting a PCE record of 6.7% for flexible FAPbBr₃ ST-PSCs. The champion device delivered the record LUE of 3.74% and is plotted against reported flexible ST-PSCs in **Figure 5d**. The CIE chromaticity diagram (1931) is used to represent the CIE coordinates of the flexible ST-PSC device under AM1.5G (air mass 1.5 global) light conditions in **Figure 5e**. To provide readers with an understanding of the AVT of the fabricated cell (55%), we captured a photographic image comparing the view of the Roman Colosseum without any filtering and the view when the camera is filtered by a flexible ST-PSC shown in **Figure 5f**. This image serves as a visual representation of the transparency and color index of the flexible ST-PSC when applied to transparent surfaces such windows to form a tinted architectural glass.

Figure 5. (a) The current voltage and power curve of 2.9 cm² mini-module. (b) The photograph of the flexible semitransparent mini-module. (c) PCE and AVT of flexible ST-PSCs along with their potential application areas²⁹. (d) LUE and AVT of flexible ST-PSCs and their maximum theoretical limit⁶⁶. (e) The CIE chromaticity diagram (1931)

presenting color coordinates of the flexible ST-PSC under AM1.5G illumination. (f) Photograph showing the view of Colosseum through the flexible ST-PSC.

Conclusions

In summary, we presented the fabrication and characterization of flexible and transparent perovskite solar cells with FAPbBr₃ absorber for the first time. We have demonstrated the positive effect of potassium treatment on the SnO₂/FAPbBr₃ interface and investigated the effect of HTL on the performance, bifaciality factor, and stability of devices. Best solar cells showed up to 55% AVT and a bifaciality factor approaching unity which results in similar performance from both sides. Record efficiencies of 6.8% under AM1.5G conditions, and 18.7% PCE under indoor illumination is obtained for flexible FAPbBr₃-based perovskite. In addition, flexible FAPbBr₃-based minimodules fabricated for the first time achieving a PCE of 4.8% and a high geometrical fill factor up to 98%. We highlight the feasibility of the flex-ST-PSCs, demonstrating their transparency and taking advantage of the high bifaciality factor up to 98%, allowing electric power generation from both side under sunlight and indoor lighting. The flexibility of cells makes them ideal for integrated transparent photovoltaic applications as an efficient and versatile energy solution.

Experimental Section

Materials. Formamidinium bromide (FABr, $\geq 99.99\%$), iso-Pentylammonium chloride, and neo-Pentylammonium chloride were purchased from Greatcell Solar Materials. Lead(II) bromide (PbBr₂) for the perovskite precursor (99.99%) was purchased from Tokyo Chemical Industry (TCI). Poly[bis(4-phenyl)(2,4,6-trimethylphenyl) amine] (PTAA, 10 kDa) and Poly[N,N'-bis(4-butylphenyl)-N,N'-bisphenylbenzidine] (PTPD, 10–30 kDa) were purchased from Solaris Chem. Tin(IV) oxide (SnO₂) colloidal nanoparticles in water (15% wt) were purchased from Alpha-Aesar, Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, $\geq 99.99\%$), potassium chloride (KCl, 99.0%), toluene (99.5%), tert-butylpyridine (TBP, 96%), Li bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (99.95%), acetonitrile (99.8%), and 2-propanol (99.5%) were purchased from Sigma- Aldrich. PET/ITO substrates (LR15) were purchased from Solutia Performance Films with 125 μm thickness and sheet resistance of 15 Ω/sq .

Device Fabrication. PET/ITO substrates were etched by laser (model) and cut in 2.5×2.5 cm² substrate sizes. The substrates were washed in ultrasonic bath using detergent, water, and 2-propanol and then treated under UV-Ozone for 15 minutes. SnO₂ nanoparticles (15 %wt) were spin coated with the speed of 6000 rpm for 35 s and then annealed at 100 °C for 60 minutes. For the potassium treated samples, 50 mM aqueous solution of KCl were spin coated at 3000 rpm for 30 s followed by annealing at 100 °C for 15 minutes. Substrates UV-Ozone treated right before the perovskite deposition and a 1.4 M solution of FAPbBr₃ in DMSO is deposited at 4000 rpm, 20s followed by anti-solvent dripping of ethyl-acetate at the 10th second. The substrates annealed at 80 °C for 10 minutes. neo-Pentylammonium chloride and iso-Pentylammonium chloride (1 mg of each) were dissolved in 1 ml of Isopropyl alcohol and spin coated on the perovskite layer to passivate defects as reported in our previous work⁴⁴. For PTAA and PTPD, 10 mg/ml solution in toluene containing 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{ml}$ TPB and 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{ml}$ Li-TFSI salt (170 mg/ml in acetonitrile) was deposited at 4000 rpm for 20 s. Finally, 150 nm of ITO was sputtered on top using power using an industrial

in-line magnetron sputtering (KENOSISTEC S.R.L., KS 400 In-Line) with the same procedure to our previous studies^{39,44}. For modules, P1, P2 and P3 etching processes have been performed by using a raster scanning laser (Wophotonics, Yb:KGW, $\lambda = 355$ nm, 5 ps, pulsed at 2000 kHz with a fluence per pulse for patterning cells and for P1, P2 and P3 of 34.33, 18.06 and 16.68 mJ cm⁻², respectively). P2 is performed by placing 6 lines beside different fluences of ~ 1 mJ cm⁻² difference, with an average fluence per pulse of 18.06 mJ cm⁻². The module layout is composed by a 25 × 25 mm² substrate size, formed by 2 series connected cells with 7.38 mm × 19.65 mm cell width and height, P1-P2-P3 interconnection of 160 μ m, 2.9cm² active area and 97.83% geometrical fill factor.

Characterizations. All solar cells were measured under standard AM1.5 conditions using a class A solar simulator (ABET Sun 2000) with an aperture area of 0.3 cm². A Si reference cell (RR226-O, RERA Solutions) was used for calibration of the sun simulator. J–V measurements under forward and reverse scan directions with the scan rate of 200 mV/s and voltage steps of 50 mV were done using Arkeo platform (Cicci Research s.r.l.). Indoor PV measurements were performed using a custom-made system⁶⁷ using a white LED (Osram Parathom Classic P25) as the light source, and a Keithley 2461 SourceMeter SMU instrument. To prevent reflection and noise in the measurement, the measurement setup box is provided with black walls and a black curtain covers the entrance during the measurement. The illuminance was calibrated with the confidence interval of 2% using AvaSpec-ULS2048CL-EVO spectrometer calibrated with a NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology)- traceable halogen light source (AvaLight-HAL-CALISP50-MINI). Average Visible transmittance (AVT) was calculated by integration of the transmission spectrum, taking into account the photopic response of the human eye and AM 1.5G photon flux³⁵. All stability test storage and measurements were performed in an ambient environment (20-30% RH) and at room temperature. The measurements for bending and storage stability tests were done under AM1.5 G light illuminations and both forward and reverse voltage biases were measured. The light soaking test is measured with ARKEO Light soaker (VIS version) with LED light sources calibrated at 0.7 sun intensity. The external quantum efficiency (EQE) spectra, transient photovoltage (TPV), and transient photocurrent (TPC), were measured using a measurement system from Arkeo–Cicci research s.r.l. The scanning electron micro- copy images were captured using a TESCAN MIRA microscope. A Rigaku SmartLab SE was used to measure X-ray diffraction patterns. Olympus Lext OLS 3100 is used to obtain optical microscopy images.

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Supporting information

Supplementary tables, Hyperspectral PL imaging, Radiative Limit, PL Models, Transient Measurements Indoor Measurement Conditions, Bending Stability Test, Geometrical Fill Factor, transmittance and reflectance of PSCs, optical loss analysis of PSCs, Maximum Power Point Tracking, and Light Soaking Test.

TOC

References

- (1) Green, M. A.; Dunlop, E. D.; Siefert, G.; Yoshita, M.; Kopidakis, N.; Bothe, K.; Hao, X. Solar Cell Efficiency Tables (Version 61). *Prog. Photovolt.* **2023**, *31* (1), 3–16.
- (2) Park, J.; Kim, J.; Yun, H.-S.; Paik, M. J.; Noh, E.; Mun, H. J.; Kim, M. G.; Shin, T. J.; Seok, S. I. Controlled Growth of Perovskite Layers with Volatile Alkylammonium Chlorides. *Nature* **2023**, *616* (7958), 724–730.
- (3) Ma, Y.; Lu, Z.; Su, X.; Zou, G.; Zhao, Q. Recent Progress toward Commercialization of Flexible Perovskite Solar Cells: From Materials and Structures to Mechanical Stabilities. *Adv. Energy Sustain. Res.* **2023**, *4* (1), 2200133.
- (4) Gao, Y.; Huang, K.; Long, C.; Ding, Y.; Chang, J.; Zhang, D.; Etgar, L.; Liu, M.; Zhang, J.; Yang, J. Flexible Perovskite Solar Cells: From Materials and Device Architectures to Applications. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2022**, *7* (4), 1412–1445.
- (5) Chen, Z.; Cheng, Q.; Chen, H.; Wu, Y.; Ding, J.; Wu, X.; Yang, H.; Liu, H.; Chen, W.; Tang, X.; Lu, X.; Li, Y.; Li, Y. Perovskite Grain-Boundary Manipulation Using Room-Temperature Dynamic Self-Healing “Ligaments” for Developing Highly Stable Flexible Perovskite Solar Cells with 23.8% Efficiency. *Adv. Mater.* **2023**, *35* (18), e2300513.
- (6) McGovern, L.; Garnett, E. C.; Veenstra, S.; van der Zwaan, B. A Techno-Economic Perspective on Rigid and Flexible Perovskite Solar Modules. *Sustain. Energy Fuels* **2023**, *7* (21), 5259–5270.

- (7) Podapangi, S. K.; Jafarzadeh, F.; Mattiello, S.; Korukonda, T. B.; Singh, A.; Beverina, L.; Brown, T. M. Green Solvents, Materials, and Lead-Free Semiconductors for Sustainable Fabrication of Perovskite Solar Cells. *RSC Adv.* **2023**, *13* (27), 18165–18206.
- (8) Holzhey, P.; Prettl, M.; Collavini, S.; Chang, N. L.; Saliba, M. Toward Commercialization with Lightweight, Flexible Perovskite Solar Cells for Residential Photovoltaics. *Joule* **2023**, *7* (2), 257–271.
- (9) Hu, Y.; Niu, T.; Liu, Y.; Zhou, Y.; Xia, Y.; Ran, C.; Wu, Z.; Song, L.; Müller-Buschbaum, P.; Chen, Y.; Huang, W. Flexible Perovskite Solar Cells with High Power-per-Weight: Progress, Application, and Perspectives. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2021**, *6* (8), 2917–2943.
- (10) Kang, S.; Jeong, J.; Cho, S.; Yoon, Y. J.; Park, S.; Lim, S.; Kim, J. Y.; Ko, H. Ultrathin, Lightweight and Flexible Perovskite Solar Cells with an Excellent Power-per-Weight Performance. *J. Mater. Chem. A Mater. Energy Sustain.* **2019**, *7* (3), 1107–1114.
- (11) Wu, X.; Xu, G.; Yang, F.; Chen, W.; Yang, H.; Shen, Y.; Wu, Y.; Chen, H.; Xi, J.; Tang, X.; Cheng, Q.; Chen, Y.; Ou, X.-M.; Li, Y.; Li, Y. Realizing 23.9% Flexible Perovskite Solar Cells via Alleviating the Residual Strain Induced by Delayed Heat Transfer. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2023**, 3750–3759.
- (12) Wu, Y.; Xu, G.; Xi, J.; Shen, Y.; Wu, X.; Tang, X.; Ding, J.; Yang, H.; Cheng, Q.; Chen, Z.; Li, Y.; Li, Y. In Situ Crosslinking-Assisted Perovskite Grain Growth for Mechanically Robust Flexible Perovskite Solar Cells with 23.4% Efficiency. *Joule* **2023**, *7* (2), 398–415.
- (13) Liu, J.; Ye, T.; Yu, D.; Liu, S. F.; Yang, D. Recoverable Flexible Perovskite Solar Cells for Next-Generation Portable Power Sources. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed Engl.* **2023**, *62* (40), e202307225.
- (14) Yang, Y.; Hoang, M. T.; Bhardwaj, A.; Wilhelm, M.; Mathur, S.; Wang, H. Perovskite Solar Cells Based Self-Charging Power Packs: Fundamentals, Applications and Challenges. *Nano Energy* **2022**, *94* (106910), 106910.
- (15) Tu, Y.; Wu, J.; Xu, G.; Yang, X.; Cai, R.; Gong, Q.; Zhu, R.; Huang, W. Perovskite Solar Cells for Space Applications: Progress and Challenges. *Adv. Mater.* **2021**, *33* (21).
<https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.202006545>.
- (16) De Rossi, F.; Taheri, B.; Bonomo, M.; Gupta, V.; Renno, G.; Yaghoobi Nia, N.; Rech, P.; Frost, C.; Cazzaniga, C.; Quagliotto, P.; Di Carlo, A.; Barolo, C.; Ottavi, M.; Brunetti, F. Neutron Irradiated Perovskite Films and Solar Cells on PET Substrates. *Nano Energy* **2022**, *93* (106879), 106879.
- (17) Müller, D.; Jiang, E.; Rivas-Lazaro, P.; Baretzky, C.; Loukeris, G.; Bogati, S.; Paetel, S.; Irvine, S. J. C.; Oklobia, O.; Jones, S.; Lamb, D.; Richter, A.; Siefer, G.; Lackner, D.; Helmers, H.; Teixeira, C.; Forgács, D.; Freitag, M.; Bradford, D.; Shen, Z.; Zimmermann, B.; Würfel, U. Indoor Photovoltaics for the Internet-of-Things – A Comparison of State-of-the-Art Devices from Different Photovoltaic Technologies. *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2023**, *6* (20), 10404–10414.
- (18) Wojciechowski, K.; Forgács, D. Commercial Applications of Indoor Photovoltaics Based on Flexible Perovskite Solar Cells. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2022**, *7* (10), 3729–3733.
- (19) Beynon, D.; Parvazian, E.; Hooper, K.; McGettrick, J.; Patidar, R.; Dunlop, T.; Wei, Z.; Davies, P.; Garcia-Rodriguez, R.; Carnie, M.; Davies, M.; Watson, T. All-Printed Roll-to-Roll Perovskite Photovoltaics Enabled by Solution-Processed Carbon Electrode. *Adv. Mater.* **2023**, e2208561.
- (20) Kim, Y. Y.; Yang, T.-Y.; Suhonen, R.; Kemppainen, A.; Hwang, K.; Jeon, N. J.; Seo, J. Roll-to-Roll Gravure-Printed Flexible Perovskite Solar Cells Using Eco-Friendly Antisolvent Bathing with Wide Processing Window. *Nat. Commun.* **2020**, *11* (1), 5146.
- (21) Shi, B.; Duan, L.; Zhao, Y.; Luo, J.; Zhang, X. Semitransparent Perovskite Solar Cells: From Materials and Devices to Applications. *Adv. Mater.* **2020**, *32* (3), e1806474.
- (22) Matteocci, F.; Rossi, D.; Castriotta, L. A.; Ory, D.; Mejaouri, S.; der Maur, M. A.; Sauvage, F.; Cacovich, S.; Di Carlo, A. Wide Bandgap Halide Perovskite Absorbers for Semi-Transparent Photovoltaics: From Theoretical Design to Modules. *Nano Energy* **2022**, *101* (107560), 107560.
- (23) Skafi, Z.; Xu, J.; Mottaghitlab, V.; Mivehi, L.; Taheri, B.; Jafarzadeh, F.; Podapangi, S. K.; Altamura, D.; Guascito, M. R.; Barba, L.; Giannini, C.; Rizzo, A.; De Rossi, F.; Javanbakht Lomeri, H.; Sorbello, L.;

- Matteocci, F.; Brunetti, F.; Brown, T. M. Highly Efficient Flexible Perovskite Solar Cells on Polyethylene Terephthalate Films via Dual Halide and Low-dimensional Interface Engineering for Indoor Photovoltaics. *Sol. RRL* **2023**. <https://doi.org/10.1002/solr.202300324>.
- (24) Bing, J.; Caro, L. G.; Talathi, H. P.; Chang, N. L.; Mckenzie, D. R.; Ho-Baillie, A. W. Y. Perovskite Solar Cells for Building Integrated Photovoltaics—Glazing Applications. *Joule* **2022**, *6* (7), 1446–1474.
- (25) Li, Q.; Zheng, Y.; Guo, X.; Zhang, G.; Ding, G.; Shi, Y.; Li, F.; Sun, M.; Shao, Y. Interface Engineering Enhances the Photovoltaic Performance of Wide Bandgap FAPbBr₃ Perovskite for Application in Low-light Environments. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2023**. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.202303729>.
- (26) Xu, J.; Podapangi, S. K.; Reddy, S. H.; Castriotta, L. A.; Di Carlo, A.; Brown, T. M. Key Parameters and Thresholds Values for Obtaining High Performance Perovskite Solar Cells Indoors from Full Br Compositional and Bandgap Engineering. *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2023**, *6* (20), 10215–10224.
- (27) Gan, S.; Sun, H.; Li, C.; Dou, D.; Li, L. Bifacial Perovskite Solar Cells: A Universal Component That Goes beyond Albedo Utilization. *Sci. Bull. (Beijing)* **2023**, *68* (19), 2247–2267.
- (28) Yang, B.; Zhang, M.; Qiao, G.; Zhang, H. Perovskite Solar Cells: Emerging Photovoltaic Technology for Achieving Net-zero Emission Agrivoltaics Ecosystem. *Sol. RRL* **2023**. <https://doi.org/10.1002/solr.202300217>.
- (29) Traverse, C. J.; Pandey, R.; Barr, M. C.; Lunt, R. R. Emergence of Highly Transparent Photovoltaics for Distributed Applications. *Nat. Energy* **2017**, *2* (11), 849–860.
- (30) Thompson, E. P.; Bombelli, E. L.; Shubham, S.; Watson, H.; Everard, A.; D’Ardes, V.; Schievano, A.; Bocchi, S.; Zand, N.; Howe, C. J.; Bombelli, P. Tinted Semi-transparent Solar Panels Allow Concurrent Production of Crops and Electricity on the Same Cropland. *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2020**, *10* (35), 2001189.
- (31) Ou, X.-L.; Feng, J.; Xu, M.; Sun, H.-B. Semitransparent and Flexible Perovskite Solar Cell with High Visible Transmittance Based on Ultrathin Metallic Electrodes. *Opt. Lett.* **2017**, *42* (10), 1958.
- (32) He, C.; Wang, J.; Chen, S.; Zhou, Y.; Jiang, N.; Zhang, J.; Duan, Y. Resolving the Contradiction between Efficiency and Transparency of Semitransparent Perovskite Solar Cells by Optimizing Dielectric-metal-dielectric Transparent Top Electrode. *Sol. RRL* **2023**, *7* (13). <https://doi.org/10.1002/solr.202300126>.
- (33) Xie, M.; Wang, J.; Kang, J.; Zhang, L.; Sun, X.; Han, K.; Luo, Q.; Lin, J.; Shi, L.; Ma, C.-Q. Super-Flexible Perovskite Solar Cells with High Power-per-Weight on 17 μ m Thick PET Substrate Utilizing Printed Ag Nanowires Bottom and Top Electrodes. *Flex. Print. Electron.* **2019**, *4* (3), 034002.
- (34) Jeong, G.; Koo, D.; Woo, J.-H.; Choi, Y.; Son, E.; Huang, F.; Kim, J.-Y.; Park, H. Highly Efficient Self-Encapsulated Flexible Semitransparent Perovskite Solar Cells via Bifacial Cation Exchange. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2022**, *14* (29), 33297–33305.
- (35) Yang, C.; Liu, D.; Bates, M.; Barr, M. C.; Lunt, R. R. How to Accurately Report Transparent Solar Cells. *Joule* **2019**, *3* (8), 1803–1809.
- (36) Lunt, R. R. Theoretical Limits for Visibly Transparent Photovoltaics. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **2012**, *101* (4), 043902.
- (37) Eperon, G. E.; Burlakov, V. M.; Goriely, A.; Snaith, H. J. Neutral Color Semitransparent Microstructured Perovskite Solar Cells. *ACS Nano* **2014**, *8* (1), 591–598.
- (38) Yuan, L.; Wang, Z.; Duan, R.; Huang, P.; Zhang, K.; Chen, Q.; Allam, N. K.; Zhou, Y.; Song, B.; Li, Y. Semi-Transparent Perovskite Solar Cells: Unveiling the Trade-off between Transparency and Efficiency. *J. Mater. Chem. A Mater. Energy Sustain.* **2018**, *6* (40), 19696–19702.
- (39) Barichello, J.; Di Girolamo, D.; Nonni, E.; Paci, B.; Generosi, A.; Kim, M.; Levtchenko, A.; Cacovich, S.; Di Carlo, A.; Matteocci, F. Semi-transparent Blade-coated FAPbBr₃ Perovskite Solar Cells: A Scalable Low-temperature Manufacturing Process under Ambient Condition. *Sol. RRL* **2023**, *7* (3), 2200739.

- (40) Yue, W.; Yang, H.; Cai, H.; Xiong, Y.; Zhou, T.; Liu, Y.; Zhao, J.; Huang, F.; Cheng, Y.-B.; Zhong, J. Printable High-Efficiency and Stable FAPbBr₃ Perovskite Solar Cells for Multifunctional Building-Integrated Photovoltaics. *Adv. Mater.* **2023**, e2301548.
- (41) Zhu, H.; Wu, W.; Wu, Y.; Zhang, D.; Zhan, H.; Cheng, Y.; Wang, L.; Qin, C. Δ -phase Management of FAPbBr₃ for Semitransparent Solar Cells. *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **2023**, 2202827.
- (42) Liu, Y.; Kim, B. J.; Wu, H.; Boschloo, G.; Johansson, E. M. J. Efficient and Stable FAPbBr₃ Perovskite Solar Cells via Interface Modification by a Low-Dimensional Perovskite Layer. *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2021**, 4 (9), 9276–9282.
- (43) Zhang, Y.; Liang, Y.; Wang, Y.; Guo, F.; Sun, L.; Xu, D. Planar FAPbBr₃ Solar Cells with Power Conversion Efficiency above 10%. *ACS Energy Lett.* **2018**, 3 (8), 1808–1814.
- (44) Matteocci, F.; Girolamo, D. D.; Vidon, G.; Barichello, J.; Giacomo, F. D.; Jafarzadeh, F.; Paci, B.; Generosi, A.; Kim, M.; Castriotta, L. A.; Frégnaux, M.; Guillemoles, J.-F.; Schulz, P.; Ory, D.; Cacovich, S.; Carlo, A. D. Breaking 1.7V Open Circuit Voltage in Large Area Transparent Perovskite Solar Cells Using Bulk and Interfaces Passivation. *Research Square*, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-3139318/v1>.
- (45) Liu, Y.; Kim, B. J.; Wu, H.; Yuan, L.; Zhu, H.; Liu, A.; Johansson, E. M. J. Flexible Lead Bromide Perovskite Solar Cells. *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2020**, 3 (10), 9817–9823.
- (46) Park, S. Y.; Zhu, K. Advances in SnO₂ for Efficient and Stable N-i-p Perovskite Solar Cells. *Adv. Mater.* **2022**, 34 (27), e2110438.
- (47) Hidayat, R.; Nurunnizar, A. A.; Fariz, A.; Herman; Rosa, E. S.; Shobih; Oizumi, T.; Fujii, A.; Ozaki, M. Revealing the Charge Carrier Kinetics in Perovskite Solar Cells Affected by Mesoscopic Structures and Defect States from Simple Transient Photovoltage Measurements. *Sci. Rep.* **2020**, 10 (1), 19197.
- (48) Jiménez-López, J.; Cambarau, W.; Cabau, L.; Palomares, E. Charge Injection, Carriers Recombination and HOMO Energy Level Relationship in Perovskite Solar Cells. *Sci. Rep.* **2017**, 7 (1), 6101.
- (49) Mozaffari, N.; Walter, D.; White, T. P.; Bui, A. D.; Tabi, G. D.; Weber, K.; Catchpole, K. R. Unraveling the Role of Energy Band Alignment and Mobile Ions on Interfacial Recombination in Perovskite Solar Cells. *Sol. RRL* **2022**, 6 (6), 2101087.
- (50) Chen, P.; Bai, Y.; Wang, L. Minimizing Voltage Losses in Perovskite Solar Cells. *Small Struct.* **2021**, 2 (1), 2000050.
- (51) Jiang, Q.; Song, Z.; Bramante, R. C.; Ndione, P. F.; Tirawat, R.; Berry, J. J.; Yan, Y.; Zhu, K. Highly Efficient Bifacial Single-Junction Perovskite Solar Cells. *Joule* **2023**, 7 (7), 1543–1555.
- (52) Giuliano, G.; Bonasera, A.; Arrabito, G.; Pignataro, B. Semitransparent Perovskite Solar Cells for Building Integration and Tandem Photovoltaics: Design Strategies and Challenges. *Sol. RRL* **2021**, 5 (12), 2100702.
- (53) Reddy, S. H.; Di Giacomo, F.; Matteocci, F.; Castriotta, L. A.; Di Carlo, A. Holistic Approach toward a Damage-Less Sputtered Indium Tin Oxide Barrier Layer for High-Stability Inverted Perovskite Solar Cells and Modules. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2022**, 14 (45), 51438–51448.
- (54) Wang, K.-L.; Zhou, Y.-H.; Lou, Y.-H.; Wang, Z.-K. Perovskite Indoor Photovoltaics: Opportunity and Challenges. *Chem. Sci.* **2021**, 12 (36), 11936–11954.
- (55) Cacovich, S.; Vidon, G.; Degani, M.; Legrand, M.; Gouda, L.; Puel, J.-B.; Vaynzof, Y.; Guillemoles, J.-F.; Ory, D.; Grancini, G. Imaging and Quantifying Non-Radiative Losses at 23% Efficient Inverted Perovskite Solar Cells Interfaces. *Nat. Commun.* **2022**, 13 (1), 2868.
- (56) Stolterfoht, M.; Wolff, C. M.; Márquez, J. A.; Zhang, S.; Hages, C. J.; Rothhardt, D.; Albrecht, S.; Burn, P. L.; Meredith, P.; Unold, T.; Neher, D. Visualization and Suppression of Interfacial Recombination for High-Efficiency Large-Area Pin Perovskite Solar Cells. *Nat. Energy* **2018**, 3 (10), 847–854.
- (57) Katahara, J. K.; Hillhouse, H. W. Quasi-Fermi Level Splitting and Sub-Bandgap Absorptivity from Semiconductor Photoluminescence. *J. Appl. Phys.* **2014**, 116 (17). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4898346>.

- (58) Milotti, V.; Cacovich, S.; Ceratti, D. R.; Ory, D.; Barichello, J.; Matteocci, F.; Di Carlo, A.; Sheverdyaeva, P. M.; Schulz, P.; Moras, P. Degradation and Self-healing of FAPbBr₃ Perovskite under Soft-X-ray Irradiation. *Small Methods* **2023**, *7* (9). <https://doi.org/10.1002/smt.202300222>.
- (59) Caprioglio, P.; Stolterfoht, M.; Wolff, C. M.; Unold, T.; Rech, B.; Albrecht, S.; Neher, D. On the Relation between the Open-circuit Voltage and Quasi-Fermi Level Splitting in Efficient Perovskite Solar Cells. *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2019**, *9* (33). <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201901631>.
- (60) Kanda, H.; Uzum, A.; Baranwal, A. K.; Peiris, T. A. N.; Umeyama, T.; Imahori, H.; Segawa, H.; Miyasaka, T.; Ito, S. Analysis of Sputtering Damage on *I*–*V* Curves for Perovskite Solar Cells and Simulation with Reversed Diode Model. *J. Phys. Chem. C Nanomater. Interfaces* **2016**, *120* (50), 28441–28447.
- (61) Rombach, F. M.; Haque, S. A.; Macdonald, T. J. Lessons Learned from Spiro-OMeTAD and PTAA in Perovskite Solar Cells. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2021**, *14* (10), 5161–5190.
- (62) Zardetto, V.; Brown, T. M.; Reale, A.; Di Carlo, A. Substrates for Flexible Electronics: A Practical Investigation on the Electrical, Film Flexibility, Optical, Temperature, and Solvent Resistance Properties. *J. Polym. Sci. B Polym. Phys.* **2011**, *49* (9), 638–648.
- (63) Cerrillo, J. G.; Distler, A.; Matteocci, F.; Forberich, K.; Wagner, M.; Basu, R.; Castriotta, L. A.; Jafarzadeh, F.; Brunetti, F.; Yang, F.; Li, N.; Mendoza, A. N. C.; Di Carlo, A.; Brabec, C. J.; Egelhaaf, H.-J. Matching the Photocurrent of 2-terminal Mechanically-stacked Perovskite/Organic Tandem Solar Modules by Varying the Cell Width. *Sol. RRL* **2023**. <https://doi.org/10.1002/solr.202300767>.
- (64) Jafarzadeh, F.; Castriotta, L. A.; De Rossi, F.; Ali, J.; Di Giacomo, F.; Di Carlo, A.; Matteocci, F.; Brunetti, F. All-Blade-Coated Flexible Perovskite Solar Cells & Modules Processed in Air from a Sustainable Dimethyl Sulfoxide (DMSO)-Based Solvent System. *Sustain. Energy Fuels* **2023**, *7* (9), 2219–2228.
- (65) Rakocevic, L.; Mundt, L. E.; Gehlhaar, R.; Merckx, T.; Aernouts, T.; Schubert, M. C.; Glunz, S. W.; Poortmans, J. Loss Analysis in Perovskite Photovoltaic Modules. *Sol. RRL* **2019**, *3* (12). <https://doi.org/10.1002/solr.201900338>.
- (66) Almora, O.; Baran, D.; Bazan, G. C.; Cabrera, C. I.; Erten-Ela, S.; Forberich, K.; Guo, F.; Hauch, J.; Ho-Baillie, A. W. Y.; Jacobsson, T. J.; Janssen, R. A. J.; Kirchartz, T.; Kopidakis, N.; Loi, M. A.; Lunt, R. R.; Mathew, X.; McGehee, M. D.; Min, J.; Mitzi, D. B.; Nazeeruddin, M. K.; Nelson, J.; Nogueira, A. F.; Paetzold, U. W.; Rand, B. P.; Rau, U.; Snaith, H. J.; Unger, E.; Vaillant-Roca, L.; Yang, C.; Yip, H.-L.; Brabec, C. J. Device Performance of Emerging Photovoltaic Materials (Version 3). *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2022**, 2203313.
- (67) De Rossi, F.; Pontecorvo, T.; Brown, T. M. Characterization of Photovoltaic Devices for Indoor Light Harvesting and Customization of Flexible Dye Solar Cells to Deliver Superior Efficiency under Artificial Lighting. *Appl. Energy* **2015**, *156*, 413–422.